

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SELF-AWARENESS OF CHILDREN AT PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE

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According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev "On measures to fundamentally improve the management of the preschool education system" (September 30, 2017, No. PF-5198), the field of preschool education is considered the primary link of the continuous education system, and it is the education of a healthy and well-rounded child in all aspects. and it is shown to be of great importance in preparing for school [1].

Improving the quality and effectiveness of education, improving its organizational and methodological aspects, based on the reforms implemented in our republic, modern socio-economic conditions, labor market and society's needs, is an urgent problem.

Further development of the educational system in terms of developing the self-awareness of children of primary school age is required to introduce structural changes, manage the dynamics of their development, introduce an effective procedure for managing continuous education and personnel training, and form a system for monitoring the quality of education. Also, raising the quality of education, management, and training of specialists to a new level in our country requires the organization of research and development activities in accordance with the innovative activities of enterprises and institutions.

The healthy and mature growth of children is directly related to the development of self-awareness. The roots of this idea are deep and extremely wide-ranging, based on pedagogical-psychological theories and concepts developed by advanced scientists, thinkers and scientists.

During the pre-school age, the child shows a very high level of interest in what he is learning. Because childhood is the most interesting period of human life. It is important to effectively use childhood curiosity and direct it to the necessary areas of a child's life. Another important aspect of the development of self-awareness during preschool education is that it serves as the first pedagogical-psychological influence

tool aimed at socializing the child (turning him into a real member of society, a citizen of the state).

The perspective of preschool children's development largely depends on the socialization factor. The development of self-awareness of children of junior school age is related to the achievement of a certain level of physical development at each age stage, the formation of individual self-awareness.

The main goal of developing self-awareness is to form a conscious attitude to a healthy lifestyle, to teach children from a young age to live in harmony with themselves and the world around them .

There are three approaches to this issue:

1. Me
2. My body
3. Healthy marriage style

"I" orientation tasks:

- *to the child of a person essence to open, own i of individuality, to himself characteristic not to be repeated to understand help to give*
- *to people faith in life love, "For being me!" availability feelings formation;*
- *self respect do, optimism, own to the family, own development of dependence on relatives and friends.*

The goals of the course "My organism":

- *formation of the child's initial knowledge about his organism, his body and health;*
- *people with systematic knowledge in relation and humanity the basics create*
- *" Healthy marriage style " direction goals:*
- *body, mind and soul culture formation ;*
- *in children own body care to do desire wake up, they ga to himself care to do methods to teach*
- *own power and opportunities to believe, himself with to be proud to teach*

To start working on these tasks, we give an example of children's diagnostic exercises in the direction of "Healthy lifestyle".

Its purpose is to form a stable life position in relation to one's own health and the people around it, to expand children's knowledge about the benefits of a healthy lifestyle.

The result of diagnostic exercises:

If the child has the opportunity to realize his knowledge during various activities, the process of self-realization of the child will be complete. In turn, the presented knowledge should encourage him to do so, stimulate his activity.

Material appropriation speed and his of knowledge depth is individual. A lot thing of the child gender, he collected of experience to nature, his emotional and to know of the fields development features depend

Various of materials content and their features according to the child main activity is determined, this while done being increased to the task complete suitable will come In one case this game, in another - exercise, in the third - training, study be activity I can. Other all types of activities i acts as a filler, i.e main activity present which does not things fill it up. Job forms - collective, small groups can be individual.

For example, to children body about expand your imagination for " Internal organs ", " Our a schematic image of a person like our assistants with familiar life work in topics trainings will be held . Also " Small assistants ", " Who can tell a lot actions" games, " Family vacation on ", " Family photo " conversations through expanding the imagination of his family possible Such training can be done in the morning, during training, during a walk and in the evening.

It is possible to ensure the participation of parents in such activities. Parents' opinions are sought in the form of questionnaires, advice, information sheets, etc.

Such activities on the development of self-awareness of children of junior school age help children to develop a vision of themselves, a sense of self-esteem, self-esteem, personal qualities and characteristics (name, patronymic, surname). General areas of development of self-awareness of children of junior school age include teaching people about infancy, preschool, school age, youth, old age, appearance of age and gender characteristics, family, neighborhood relations, and cultural traditions of their family.

The method of "working in small groups", which is one of the available pedagogical technologies for the development of self-awareness of children of primary school age, shows that when used in all classes, the level of knowledge of children increases, they can express their opinions independently, and the active participation of everyone in the training process increases. In this case, the children in the group are divided into several groups and given a task, a mixed problem or a problem based on a question. Solving a problem requires the participation and interaction of all members of the group. The main advantage of the method of working in small groups is that children with low mastery are helped not only by the teacher, but also by their classmates [2].

Group instruction requires continuous change when applied from elementary school age to high school. Because the effectiveness of training may not be high when groups are organized for the first time in small groups . One of the reasons for

this is that children do not immediately get used to working in groups. In order to acquire such skills, they need to be mentally prepared through the reminder of working in special groups.

In this note:

- listen carefully to your teammate and understand his opinion, if you don't understand, ask again;
- learn to express your opinion briefly and clearly;
- if you do not agree with the opinion of your group mate, explain why;
- if they do not agree with your opinion, the reason I 'm sorry ;
- if your mind is not stealing prove if they give, your mistakes admit ol ing and others.

It should not be forgotten that the solution of the given tasks depends on each member of the group. It is necessary to create a friendly, at least neutral relationship, atmosphere based on solidarity among group members.

Also, it is advisable to use the following forms of training in the development of self-awareness of children of junior school age:

- competition;
- creative assignments;
- a trip to the animal world, etc.

Small groups in formation voluntariness principle compliance will be done. In a group to work did not want the child force possible not Groups temporary or constant can also die. A group is also the same or different level from children organize to find can Har one's unique positive sides and has disadvantages. Organized with children of junior school age done groups died temporarily ok Later on constant guru hlar form goes

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